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**A STUDY OF SOCIAL MEDIA LANGUAGE PRACTICES AMONG MULTILINGUAL
NIGERIAN YOUTHS**

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Abstract

This study applies Computer-Mediated Communication Theory (CMCT) by Joseph Walther 1992 and Social Identity Theory (Tajfel and Turner [1979](#)) to examine how young people in Nigeria construct and negotiate language practices within social media environments. Data were collected through systematic observation of online interactions across platforms such as WhatsApp, Instagram, X (formerly Twitter), and TikTok. Findings reveal that youths employ multimodal strategies such as abbreviations, acronyms, emojis, hashtags, code-switching, and visual resources (images and videos) to facilitate communication. Within the CMDT framework, these practices are understood as discourse choices shaped by the affordances and constraints of social media platforms. The study highlights how Nigerian youths creatively exploit these technological and linguistic resources to assert identity, foster group belonging, and navigate multilingual interaction in digital spaces. Ultimately, this research underscores the dynamic interplay between platform-specific features, cultural context, and discourse practices, offering insights into the evolving nature of computer-mediated communication.

Keywords: Social media, Language Practices, Multilingualism, Emoji, Virtual resources Code-switching,

1.1 Introduction

The rise of social media has fundamentally reshaped how young people communicate and construct identities, particularly in multilingual societies such as Nigeria. Platforms like WhatsApp, Instagram, Twitter (now X), and TikTok have become linguistic laboratories where creativity flourishes. Nigerian youths employ these digital spaces to negotiate cultural affiliations, signal group membership, and perform identity, a trend noted by Jannis and Androutsopoulos, (82-261) who emphasizes that online communication often serves as a site of identity performance and cultural exchange. Similarly, danah boyd (14) highlights how young people use networked publics to engage in practices of identity construction and social belonging.

As M. A. K. Halliday (2) observes, language is not simply a conduit for transmitting information but a social semiotic, a resource for constructing meaning and performing identities. Digital environments expand this semiotic capacity by offering multimodal resources such as emojis, hashtags, memes, and abbreviations, which frequently deviate from conventional grammar (Crystal 3–7). While scholars have increasingly documented global social media practices, (David Seargeant and Caroline Tagg (134) argue that the localized, cultural dimensions of digital language use demand closer attention. This study addresses that gap by focusing specifically on Nigerian youths' multilingual digital repertoires.

In the last decade, social media has become more than a medium for information exchange; it has evolved into a central arena for identity construction, cultural negotiation, and linguistic innovation. Boyd (201) explains that networked publics function as spaces where youth experiment with language and identity, adapting communication practices to digital affordances .

This phenomenon is particularly significant among Nigerian youths, often described as “digital natives,” the first generation to grow up fully immersed in networked technologies (Prensky 1).

Social media, for them, functions both as an extension of offline social networks and as an autonomous sphere where hybrid communication styles emerge.

One defining feature of Nigerian digital discourse is its multilingual character. Although the country hosts over [500](#) languages, English, Nigerian Pidgin, Hausa, Yoruba, and Igbo dominate online interaction. Youths often blend these languages, engaging in code-switching and translanguaging, practices Ofelia García and Li Wei describe as the strategic blending of linguistic repertoires to communicate and perform identity (García and Wei 22). Such practices serve pragmatic purposes, such as efficiency and clarity, but also symbolic ones, including the assertion of cultural pride and group belonging (Androutsopoulos [261](#); Ogunyemi and Okon [202](#)).

Equally crucial are platform affordances that shape communicative choices. For instance, Twitter’s [280](#)-character limit encourages brevity, while Instagram privileges visual storytelling, often supported by captions and emojis (Kaplan and Haenlein 59–68; Danesi 22). WhatsApp fosters real-time, informal exchanges, frequently in multilingual registers. Allan Bell’s (145-204) concept of “audience design” clarifies how these adaptations reflect not only platform constraints but also peer expectations.

Finally, Nigerian youths’ digital practices intersect with broader sociocultural dynamics.

Hashtags such as #EndSARS exemplify digitally mediated civic participation, while memes and emojis enrich meaning, adding affective, humorous, and culturally specific layers (Ibrahim; Crystal 5; Danesi 33–41). Such innovations destabilize traditional hierarchies of “correct” language and blur the boundaries between formal and informal registers (Sharma [206](#)).

Against this background, this study focuses on a central objective specifically the types of language do Nigerian youths commonly use on social media platforms, it also examines how abbreviations, code-switching, emojis, hashtags, and other linguistic features function in online interactions. By exploring these practices, the study aims to contribute to a richer understanding of the evolving relationship between language, technology, and youth identity in Nigeria. Particularly in relation to identity construction, group belonging, and civic participation. By focusing on these dynamics, this study explores how Nigerian youths creatively exploit the intersection of linguistic resources, platform affordances, and sociocultural contexts to develop novel forms of expression.

LITRETURE RVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review, Empirical Review and Theoretical Framework

The study of social media language platforms at the intersection of sociolinguistics, digital media studies, and identity theory, reflecting how technology reshapes communication norms and cultural expression (Crystal 2; Tagg and Seargeant 65–83). Scholars such as Crystal (2) have described the emergence of Netspeak as a hybrid form of communication characterized by abbreviations, acronyms, and novel orthography that often defies traditional grammar while evolving rapidly within user communities. Similarly, Lenhart, Madden, and Hitlin (48) observed that adolescents are prolific innovators of abbreviations and emotive symbols as a response to the speed and informality of instant messaging. Danesi (15-45) adds that emojis and visual symbols function as a “parallel semiotic system” that enriches textual communication with affective nuance. Within youth communities, these elements are not simply decorative but serve as tools for identity signaling, humor, and solidarity. For instance, emojis such as 🔥 and 😊 have

developed culturally specific meanings that extend far beyond their literal representations. In multilingual societies such as Nigeria, social media has become a fertile ground for code-switching and translanguaging. García and Wei (22) define translanguaging as the flexible and strategic blending of languages to communicate and construct identity. Studies by Androutsopoulos (185–205) and Blom and Gumperz (407–434) show that online users often alternate linguistic codes to achieve in-group solidarity, humor, and resistance to dominant linguistic norms. Isaiah (57-74) documents how Nigerian youths on WhatsApp and Instagram deploy code-switching deliberately as a strategy for intimacy and cultural expression. Sharma (201) further explains that these practices represent the evolution of hybrid linguistic forms that embody contemporary youth identities.

Another important strand of research concerns the ways that platform affordances shape digital language. Kaplan and Haenlein (61-64) argue that the constraints and features of each social media site significantly influence linguistic practices. For example, Twitter’s brevity fosters concise syntax and hashtag use; Instagram privileges visual content supplemented by short captions; and WhatsApp enables real-time, multilingual chatting. Bell’s concept of audience design clarifies how users strategically adjust their linguistic repertoires depending on the audience (145–146). Nigerian youths often employ formal English on professional platforms such as LinkedIn, hybrid Pidgin-English on WhatsApp, and slang-heavy memes on Instagram. These patterns underscore the notion that social media language is contextually situated, strategically adapted, and dynamically negotiated (4).

The relationship between language and identity is also central to this discussion. Social Identity Theory, proposed by Tajfel and Turner (1979), emphasizes that individuals construct self-concepts partly through group membership and in-group/out-group distinctions. Online, Nigerian

youths enact identity through usernames and bios (boyd 8), trending hashtags (Ibrahim 20), and hybridized language forms (Androutsopoulos 25–45). Goffman’s (255) notion of self-presentation is particularly useful in explaining how youths curate online personas by selecting linguistic styles, emojis, and symbols to reinforce social belonging. Hashtags like #EndSARS exemplify how personal expression aligns with collective identity, transforming individual voices into broader sociopolitical solidarity (Ibrahim 20).

While some scholars criticize social media discourse as corrosive to conventional literacy (Sharma 201), others highlight its positive role in fostering digital literacy and adaptive communication skills (Crystal 2; Lenhart et al. 14–17). Gee argues that participation in digital communities cultivates audience awareness, multimodal composition skills, and the ability to shift communication strategies (4). García and Wei further contend that such practices, particularly in multilingual contexts, promote cultural pride and challenge dominant hierarchies of “correct” language (5–18). Rather than viewing online language use as linguistic decline, it can instead be understood as legitimate literacy and creativity, embedded in the “networked publics” of youth interaction (boyd 39). Kaplan and Haenlein likewise emphasize that social media platforms function as interactive spaces for user-generated content that allow young people to both consume and produce language reflecting their cultural backgrounds (210). Several recurring features define the discourse of social media. Lenhart, Madden, and Hitlin show how instant messaging accelerates the use of abbreviations such as LOL or BRB (205). García and Wei describe the blending of languages as an expressive resource (78–118). Danesi and Crystal argue that emojis have evolved into a semiotic system in their own right (Danesi 40–60; Crystal 1–10). Tagg highlights how hashtags and memes serve as tools of identity construction and solidarity within online communities (57). In Nigeria, these elements interact

with a unique multilingual ecology in which English, Nigerian Pidgin, Hausa, Yoruba, and Igbo blend fluidly, producing linguistic hybridity that challenges conventional boundaries between formal and informal registers (Ogunyemi and Okon [112](#); Sharma 12).

Although the evolution of social media language is well documented in Western contexts (Tagg and Seargeant [161–185](#); Androutsopoulos [202–222](#)), relatively few studies have examined the particular forms of discourse Nigerian youths employ across platforms, the role of code-switching and emoji use in identity construction, and the sociolinguistic significance of hashtags and memes within Nigerian virtual communities. This study seeks to address these gaps by providing a systematic analysis of the types of language Nigerian youth use on social media, grounded in empirical data from multilingual contexts.

3.1 Methodology

This study employs a qualitative approach to investigate the linguistic practices of Nigerian youths on social media. Data will be collected from three major platforms that dominate youth interaction in Nigeria: WhatsApp, Instagram, and Twitter (X). WhatsApp is chosen for its intimate and multilingual conversations, Instagram for its hybrid English captions enriched with emojis and visual symbols, and Twitter for its brevity, creative use of abbreviations, and trending hashtags.

The linguistic data to be gathered will include abbreviations (e.g., LOL, BTW), code-switching between English, Pidgin, and indigenous languages, emojis (🔥, 😊), hashtags (#EndSARS, #NoWahala), and memes or stylized phrases. These data will be gathered through digital observation and content analysis of naturally occurring posts, ensuring authenticity of language use in context.

To complement this, observation of some selected social media handles will be conducted with

Nigerian youths aged 18–30. All data will be thematically coded to identify recurring features and communicative functions.

The analysis will be guided by Social Identity Theory (Tajfel and Turner [1979](#)), which explains how language reflects group membership, identity assertion, and in-group solidarity, and by Computer-Mediated Communication Theory (Kaplan and Haenlein [210](#)), which explains how platform affordances and audience design shape expression. Findings will be presented in a descriptive-analytical format, illustrating how linguistic innovations systematically function as identity practices and technologically mediated behaviors in Nigerian youth discourse.

4.1 Data Presentation, Analysis, and Discussion of Findings

This study employed an observation method to collect linguistic data from social media platforms frequently used by Nigerian youths, including WhatsApp, Twitter (X), and Instagram. A total of 30 posts were systematically observed and documented over a specified period. The analysis revealed five recurring categories of linguistic features: abbreviations and acronyms, code-switching and hybrid language, emojis and visual markers, hashtags and memes, and platform-specific styles. These practices highlight how young people adapt language online to negotiate identity, enhance efficiency, and express emotion.

[4.1.1](#) Abbreviations and Acronyms

Observed posts showed pervasive use of abbreviations and acronyms such as:

LOL (Laugh Out Loud)

BRB (Be Right Back)

OMG (Oh My God)

TBH (To Be Honest)

FOMO (Fear Of Missing Out)

These forms compressed expression and conveyed familiarity. For example:

“BRB, lemme gist you later.”

Discussion: Abbreviations support Lenhart et al.'s (205) argument that digital spaces foster brevity and innovation. In the Nigerian context, their frequent use also serves as a generational marker, echoing Goffman's (17–23) claim that stylistic choices become resources for self-presentation. This aligns with Labov's principle that variation is systematic, not random, and Halliday's (2) idea of language as a semiotic tool for social meaning-making.

4.1.2 Code-Switching and Hybrid Language

Observation revealed frequent mixing of English, Nigerian Pidgin, and Hausa:

“Abeg na who sabi this p?”

“Wetin dey sup?”

“Kai, this gist dey sweet me die.”

These hybrid utterances reflected everyday speech patterns.

Discussion: This practice aligns with Androutsopoulos's (261–282) notion of multilingual online discourse as identity performance. Rather than being linguistic deficiency, it supports García and Wei's (22) concept of translanguaging, where bilingual and multilingual speakers use their full linguistic repertoire fluidly. In this sense, Nigerian youths enact Gee's (99–125) Discourse framework, signaling solidarity and cultural belonging in digital spaces.

4.1.3 Emojis and Visual Symbols

Emojis were consistently observed as substitutes for words or as emotional amplifiers:

😂😂😂 (laughter)

🔥 (approval/intensity)

❤️ (affection)

🙏 (gratitude/plea)

Example: “This party was 🔥🔥🔥!”

Discussion: Danesi (40–60) views emojis as a parallel semiotic code, a claim confirmed by these findings. Emojis enable impression management (Goffman 22–23) and strengthen group cohesion (Tagg 29). Their widespread use resonates with Social Identity Theory (Tajfel & Turner [1979](#)), as they function as symbolic resources that reinforce in-group belonging.

4.1.4 Hashtags and Memes

Observed posts revealed the strategic use of hashtags to frame identity and align with movements:

#EndSARS (political activism)

#NaijaNoDeyCarryLast (national pride)

#SmallGirlBigGod (lifestyle)

#TBT (Throwback Thursday)

Discussion: Boyd’s ([2014](#)) concept of “networked publics” and Ibrahim’s (78) work on hashtags explain how they organize discourse and signal solidarity. Hashtags embody Gee’s idea of “Discourses,” where language practices are intertwined with social values and identity. Nigerian youths use them not only for visibility but also for cultural affirmation and civic participation.

4.1.5 Platform Specific Patterns

Patterns varied across platforms:

WhatsApp: Multilingual conversations within intimate groups.

Twitter (X): Abbreviations, hashtags, and concise phrasing due to character limits.

Instagram: Hybrid captions mixing English, local idioms, and emojis to complement visuals.

Example observation: “On WhatsApp, Pidgin and Hausa blend easily, while Twitter posts are

shorter and sharper.”

Discussion: This reflects Bell’s (145–204) notion of audience design users tailor language to both the platform’s affordances and the expected audience. Kaplan and Haenlein’s (62) CMC framework also explain how platform structures shape linguistic expression. Nigerian youths display digital literacy by shifting repertoires fluidly across contexts.

4.2 Synthesis of Findings

The observed posts demonstrate that Nigerian youths’ language practices online are systematic, intentional, and culturally significant. Abbreviations, code-switching, emojis, and hashtags are not peripheral but central to how identity and solidarity are performed in digital spaces.

These findings reinforce Halliday’s idea of language as a social semiotic, Labov’s assertion that linguistic variation is socially patterned, and Tajfel & Turner’s Social Identity Theory, which emphasizes the role of group affiliation in shaping self-concept.

Far from representing linguistic decline, these practices affirm Crystal’s David (89) argument that digital language use signals creativity and adaptability. They also support Gee’s (1–24) view that emerging digital practices challenge traditional hierarchies of “correct” language, underscoring that social media is a vital arena for contemporary linguistic innovation.

5.1 Summary of Recommendations and Conclusion

The study recommends that educators integrate digital literacy into curricula by teaching abbreviations, emojis, hashtags, and code-switching as legitimate literacy practices (Crystal 89). Code-switching and translanguaging should be recognized as signs of linguistic dexterity rather than deficiency (García and Wei 22). Teaching resources must incorporate authentic examples of youth digital discourse to reflect real-world usage. Social media platforms should also enhance multilingual inclusivity by supporting Nigerian Pidgin and indigenous languages in predictive

text and emoji tools. At the same time, digital safety policies must guide youths in managing potential misinterpretations of online symbols. Civic education campaigns can leverage expressive styles such as hashtags and memes to engage young audiences (Boyd 14).

Policymakers are encouraged to develop national guidelines on digital language use while fostering dialogue on evolving online culture.

The findings confirm that Nigerian youths employ abbreviations, emojis, hashtags, and hybrid language forms strategically to perform identity, maintain solidarity, and express creativity.

These practices support Social Identity Theory (Tajfel and Turner [1979](#)) and affirm Labov's claim that variation is systematic. They also align with Computer-Mediated Communication

Theory by showing how platform affordances shape expression. Importantly, the study

challenges deficit views of digital language, instead affirming scholars such as Crystal, Danesi, and Gee, who argue that online repertoires represent legitimate, evolving literacies (Crystal 89;

Danesi 24; Gee 4).

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